

DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION OF A COMPOSITE MATERIAL MADE UP BY GLASS FIBER REINFORCED PLASTICS AND HIGH STRENGTH STEEL

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ABSTRACT

Intrinsic hybrid laminates are well established since many years in aerospace engineering, e.g. glass laminate aluminium reinforced epoxy (GLARE) is widely used as a substitute for aluminium sheets of the outer shell of modern aircrafts. The reduction of density and an increased stiffness by compounding glass fiber and aluminium makes GLARE advantageous. Driven by environmental protection acts and the need for lightweight design, material compounds attract more awareness in the automotive engineering as well. Functional components like chassis springs are well predestined for the application of glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP). Therefore, an intrinsic hybrid made up by GFRP and a high strength steel has recently been developed and characterized.

This investigation sets the focus on the interface between GFRP and steel. Double cantilever beam tests (mode I) and shear tests (mode II) are conducted in order to measure the energy release rate and the shear strength of the considered interface. A variety of interfaces with different surface treatments of the steel layers have been characterized by this approach. The results show up that good adhesion can be achieved by the use of silane and titanium dioxide primers, however, the variation within the measured mechanical properties is huge. Furthermore, the increase of the energy release rate by fiber bridging effects is considered as well and an approach for its quantitative description due to a power law is presented.

Finally the bearing strength of a multilayer hybrid laminate made up by steel and GFRP has been tested by means of a pull-out test.

1 INTRODUCTION

The importance of automotive lightweight such as aluminium, magnesium and fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) as well as high-strength steels as construction materials is increasing. However, a simple substitution of one material by another is not always viable. Sometimes a better solution is elaborated by a material compound.

There are different ways of combining materials. On the one hand in a multi-material-approach are joined by means of a conventional joining technology, which are state of the art and an automation is available. The performance of such a system of materials is limited by the strength of the joint or the strength of the weakest component. A bolted joint in a multi-material-system built up by glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP) and steel may have a significantly reduced strength compared to the strength of the mono-materials, respectively [1]. On the other hand intrinsic hybrids show a huge potential for high strength joining [2]. Another advantage of intrinsic hybrids is the superior fatigue strength compared to bare metals such as an aluminium alloy which is caused by the crack bridging effect [3]. Especially the aerospace industry applies intrinsic hybrid materials like glass laminate aluminium reinforced epoxy (GLARE) or carbon reinforced plastic aluminium laminate (CARALL) [4]. These intrinsic hybrid materials or laminates mainly consist of a light metal, e.g. aluminium and titanium, and fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) like GFRP or carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP). In this study the intrinsic hybrid laminates are made up by GFRP and a high strength steel. Considering the different chemical structures of the components, strong adhesion is achieved by the use of adhesion agents or

primers [5]. These chemical primers comprise a functional group which is chemically linked to the steel surface and another group which is chemically linked to the epoxy resin.

Two load cases are considered for the characterization of the bonding strength of the interface. The fracture toughness, mode I (opening), is evaluated by a double cantilever beam (DCB) test [6] and the shear strength, mode II (sliding), by an Edge-Shear-Test (EST) [7]. These two tests are originally designed for FRP materials so that modifications are necessary for testing of intrinsic hybrid laminates as well. Finally, the bearing strength of a local hybridization by means of GFRP and steel is analyzed by a pull-out test.

2 CHARACTERIZATION OF THE BONDED CONNECTION

2.1 Specimen Preparation

The intrinsic hybrid laminate specimens for mode I and mode II testing are made up by one layer of a bainitic steel (51CrV4) and another layer of unidirectional GFRP prepregs (E-glass fibers, epoxy resin), s. Fig. 1a. The dimensions of each rectangular specimen are denoted by its length l , thickness t , and width w . It is here agreed upon that the direction of the dimension length l is pointing into the average alignment of the unidirectional glass fibers. The layer thicknesses are $t_{\text{steel}} = 1.76$ mm for steel and $t_{\text{GFRP}} = 3$ mm for GFRP, respectively. The specimens are produced in a 3 step process, i.e., (i) chemical surface treatment of the steel, (ii) synthesis of steel with GFRP in the prepreg process, and (iii) finishing of the specimens by cutting them into the final dimensions.

(i) Chemical Surface Treatment

The steel surfaces are cleaned in a bath of isopropanol (grease removing), etched in a phosphoric acid (corrosion product removing), and flushed by isopropanol (acid removing). Then the specimens are dipped for 10 min into the primer solution, which is stirred the whole time. The applied primers are silane (labelled as #C1) and titanium dioxide (labelled as #C2). The drying of the specimens happens at a temperature of $T = 100$ °C for 15 min. The surface roughness of the chemical treated specimens, here defined by the average peak-to-valley height R_z , is $R_z = 3.3$ μm .

(ii) Synthesis

The surface treated steel plate is put together with the GFRP prepreg into a compression mold and is processed under control of pressure and temperature. At a temperature $T > 100$ °C the resin gets liquid. As soon as the hardener gets activated, the resin cures and the steel gets bonded to the epoxy resin.

(iii) Finishing

The hybrid laminate specimens are cut into pieces by means of a diamond circular saw. They serve as specimens for the DCB-Test and EST. The effective length l_{DCB} of the DCB specimens is $l_{\text{DCB}} = 163$ mm and its width $w = 25$ mm. The thickness of the layers t_{steel} and t_{GFRP} are chosen such that the individual cantilever beams made up by steel and GFRP comprise the same bending stiffness. The effective length l_{EST} of the EST specimens is $l_{\text{EST}} = 10$ mm. All reference specimens, denoted as #A, are purely made up by GFRP with a thickness of $t_{\text{reference}} = 5$ mm.

2.2 Experimental Setup

Mode I (opening) fracture toughness of the interface is determined by using a modified DCB Test according to ASTM D 5528-01 [6]. Mode II (sliding) shear strength is determined by an EST, proposed by Weidenmann et al. [7].

Mode I: Fracture Toughness

An initial crack of the length $a_0 = 50$ mm (s. Fig. 1) has been established in the DCB specimen by a thin film with anti-adhesion performance which is placed between the layers of GFRP and steel prior to the prepreg process. The load F is applied by load blocks at each layer. The quasi-static, displacement controlled test is conducted with a velocity v_t of the traverse which is always between $1 \text{ mm/min} < v_t < 3 \text{ mm/min}$ (s. Fig. 2). A length scale (s. Fig. 1b) has been applied to the intrinsic hybrid specimens so that the total crack length a can be recorded by means of an external camera system. The crack opening displacement δ (s. Fig. 1b) is measured by means of the displacement transducer and the load F by means of a load cell (s. Fig. 2).

Figure 1: Specimen for the DCB-Test a) unloaded b) loaded

Figure 2: Test setup of the DCB-Test

Mode II: Shear Strength

The specimens are loaded via two pressure plates with an offset t_{offset} between 0.5 up to 1 mm (s. Fig. 3), so that the upper pressure plate solely actuates the steel component and the lower plate the GFRP

Figure 3: a) Specimen and its dimensions b) Test setup of the EST

component. The length $l_{\text{EST}} = 10 \text{ mm}$ of the specimens is much less than $l_{\text{EST,max}} = 26.7 \text{ mm}$ so that it

fails due to the shear stress at the interface and not due to an excessive pressure parallel to the fiber alignment in the GFRP. The EST is a quasi-static, displacement controlled test, where the velocity of the traverse is chosen to be $v_t = 1$ mm/min.

2.3 Results

Mode I: Fracture Toughness.

A total of 6 specimens of each type #A, #C1 and #C2, respectively, have been tested. The energy release rate $G_I = G_I(a)$ of the DCB-Test, representing a measure for the crack resistance, are evaluated according to the modified beam theory [6] given by

$$G_I = \frac{3 \cdot F \cdot \delta}{2 \cdot w(a + |\Delta|)} \quad (1)$$

where $|\Delta|$ is a correction value which is individually determined for each specimen and measurement. The mean values of $\overline{G_I}(a)$ are fitted according to a power law

$$\overline{G_I}(a) = (a - a_0)^n + G_0 \quad (2)$$

where G_0 is a fitting parameter and a_0 the initial crack length of 50 mm (s. Fig. 4). The minimum and maximum values of $G_I(a)$ are represented by bars. The reference #A shows a rising energy release rate G_I (s. Fig. 4a). It starts at 0.5 N/mm and reaches almost up to 1.0 N/mm. A strong adhesion of steel

Figure 4: Energy release rates of a) the GFRP reference, b) silane, and c) titanium dioxide coated specimens

and GFRP can be realized by using chemical surface treatments with silane and titanium dioxide (s. Fig. 4b and 4c). The average energy release rates of specimens #C1 and #C2 are equal to or even better than that of the reference specimen #A. However, the range of measured values is much bigger for specimens of type #C1 than for type #C2 and #A. The value of G_I for specimens of type #C2 is 0.6 to 0.7 N/mm for relatively short crack lengths and approaches 1.2 N/mm for longer cracks. Specimens of type #C1 even reach its highest value at 1.4 N/mm. The average value, however, is clearly below that of type #C2. The initiation value G_{Ic} of the energy release rate, the crack resistance, is determined at the point of deviation from linearity of the load displacement curve of the DCB-Test [6].

Mode II: Shear Strength.

Each type of specimen has been tested at least 6 times. The shear strength τ_s is evaluated by

$$\tau_s = \frac{F_{\max}}{w \cdot l_{EST}} \quad (3)$$

where F_{\max} is the maximum load which is measured during the individual Edge-Shear-Test (s. Fig. 5a).

Figure 5: a) Loading curve and its maximum force F_{\max} b) Shear strength τ_s values

Specimens of reference #A show an average shear strength of $\bar{\tau}_{s\#A} = 55$ MPa with only a relatively small total spread of 10 MPa. The spread of shear strength values for specimens of type #C1 and #C2, respectively, are huge, i.e. the measured values are between 30 MPa and 60 MPa. The average shear strength of specimens of type #C1 is $\bar{\tau}_{s\#C1} = 49$ MPa and that of type #C2 with $\bar{\tau}_{s\#C2} = 43$ MPa.

3 LOCAL HYBRIDIZATION OF A BOLTED JOINT

A local hybridization for a pin joint has been analyzed. Its bearing strength is evaluated by means of a quasi-static pull-out test.

3.1 Specimen Preparation

The specimens have been manufactured by the same process mentioned in Chapter 2.1 (ii), but the cutting process has been performed by means of a water jet because of the huge dimensions of the specimens. The dimensions of the specimens, which are labelled by an index br, are given by its total length $l_{br} = 140$ mm, its thickness $t_{br} = 5$ mm, and its width $w_{br} = 36$ mm. The diameter d of the drill hole is $d = 6$ mm and its distance to the edge is 3 times this diameter. The length l_{lochyb} of the area of the local hybridization is always between $40 \leq l_{lochyb} \leq 60$ mm (s. Fig. 6). Two types of reference specimens are

Figure 6: Dimension of the specimens for evaluating the bearing stress

built up by solely using GFRP, in particular (i) a unidirectional and (ii) a multidirectional GFRP material. The unidirectional GFRP specimen is denoted as #GFRP1 and the multidirectional GFRP specimen as #GFRP2. The fiber alignments are shown in Tab. 1. Four kinds of specimens with a local hybridization,

Notation	Total Number of Layers N	Fiber Alignment towards the Load Direction α	Single Layer Thickness t in mm
#GFRP1	8	$[0^\circ]$	0.625
#GFRP2	8	$[90^\circ/0^\circ/45^\circ/0^\circ]_{\text{sym}}$	0.625

Table 1: Design of the reference GFRP specimens

which are denoted as #Hybrid1 to #Hybrid4, have been designed. The fiber alignment of the unidirectional GFRP fraction is always $\alpha = 0^\circ$. The width of the steel plates covers the whole width w_{br} of the specimen. Every specimen has a specific steel content φ which is related to a cross section area of the specimen at the drill hole (s. Fig. 7).

$$\varphi = \frac{\sum t_{steel,i}}{t_{br}} \quad (4)$$

The thickness of the steel layers is denoted by $t_{steel,i}$. The design details of the specimens #Hybrid1 to #Hybrid4 are documented in Fig. 8 and Tab. 2.

Figure 7: Detailed view of specimen #Hybrid3

Figure 8: Detailed view of the local hybridization of a pin joint for each kind

Notation	Total Number of Layers N	Specific Steel Content φ [%]	Type of Layer	Single Layer Thickness t [mm]	Single Layer Length l [mm]
#Hybrid1	3	10	GFRP	1.250	140
			Steel	0.500	40
			GFRP	1.250	140
#Hybrid2	7	15	GFRP	0.875	140
			Steel	0.250	40
			GFRP	1.250	140
			Steel	0.250	60
			GFRP	1.250	140
			Steel	0.250	40
			GFRP	0.875	140
#Hybrid3	5	20	GFRP	0.125	140
			Steel	0.500	40
			GFRP	1.500	140
			Steel	0.500	40
			GFRP	0.125	140
#Hybrid4	7	25	GFRP	0.938	140
			Steel	0.500	40
			GFRP	0.938	140
			Steel	0.250	60
			GFRP	0.938	140
			Steel	0.500	40
			GFRP	0.938	140

Table 2: Design of the specimens with the local hybridization

3.2 Experimental Setup

A pull-out test has been performed by loading the pin joint with a tensional load which is transmitted via a pin of the diameter $d_p \leq 6$ mm. This tensional load causes a static bearing stress at the drill hole (s. Fig. 9). The pull-out test is displacement controlled with a velocity of the traverse of $v_t = 3$ mm/min. The specimens are implemented torque-free in the test setup and without a clamping force at the drill hole.

Figure 9: Test setup for evaluating the bearing strength

3.3 Results

The pull-out test has been performed for at least 3 specimens of each type of specimen. The bearing strength is evaluated according to

$$\sigma_{br} = \frac{F_{br,max}}{d \cdot t_{br}} \quad (5)$$

where $F_{br,max}$ is the maximum load which is measured during the individual pull-out test (s. Fig. 10a).

Figure 10: Bearing strength σ_{br} a) loading curve and its maximum force $F_{br,max}$ b) average values

The average bearing strength $\bar{\sigma}_{br, \#GFRP1}$ of specimens #GFRP1 is $\bar{\sigma}_{br, \#GFRP1} = 207$ MPa. The average bearing strength of the multidirectional specimens #GFRP2 is $\bar{\sigma}_{br, \#GFRP2} = 517$ MPa which is 2.5 times higher than the average bearing strength $\bar{\sigma}_{br, \#GFRP1}$ of specimens #GFRP1. The average bearing strength of the specimens with a local hybridization reads $\bar{\sigma}_{br, \#Hybrid, Si} = 585$ MPa up to $\bar{\sigma}_{br, \#Hybrid4, Si} = 1262$ MPa for the specimens treated with a silane primer and $\bar{\sigma}_{br, \#Hybrid, Ti} = 538$ MPa up to $\bar{\sigma}_{br, \#Hybrid4, Ti} = 1163$ MPa for the specimens treated with a titanium dioxide primer (s. Fig. 10b). The average bearing strength values of specimens processed by use of the titanium dioxide are almost 10 % below those processed by use of the silane primer.

4 DISCUSSION

It has been observed in our investigation that the average energy release rate \bar{G}_I is not a materials constant (s. Fig 4). It is known from the literature [2] that a fiber pull-out at the GFRP leads to a progression of the energy release rate \bar{G}_I with increasing crack length a which is denoted as a fiber bridging effect (s. Fig. 11). Therefore, the test results are fitted by a power law (s. Eq. 2). The progression of \bar{G}_I can be characterized by a strengthening exponent n . Specimens of type #C1 and #C2 exhibit a strengthening exponent $n_{\#C1} = 0.18$ and $n_{\#C2} = 0.16$ with a widespread fiber pull-out. The average crack resistance \bar{G}_{Ic} is plotted as a horizontal line into the diagrams of Fig. 4 for each type of specimen. Since \bar{G}_{Ic} is always smaller than the measured values of the energy release rates \bar{G}_I , \bar{G}_{Ic} seems to represent a minimum crack resistance $K_{Ic} \sim \sqrt{\bar{G}_{Ic}}$ without the impact of fiber bridging effects.

Figure 11: Correlation between the increase of the energy release rate and the intensity of fiber pull-out

Furthermore, an incubation crack length a_{inc} for fiber bridging effects of 5 to 10 mm is indicated by the intersection of the \bar{G}_{Ic} line with the fitting curve, respectively.

The Edge-Shear-Test specimens have been analyzed by the appearance of two failure modes (s. Fig. 12). It is distinguished between a GFRP failure (s. Fig. 12, #C1), i.e. a failure of the resin matrix between the fibers, and a mixed failure (s. Fig. 12, #C2) where a failure of the resin matrix as well as of the adhesion occurs at the same fractured surface. An entire adhesion failure of a specimen does not appear. The ratios of failure modes P_i are calculated accordingly to

$$P_i = \frac{N_i}{N} \quad (6)$$

where N is total number of considered specimens, N_i the number of specimens with a dominant failure mode i , i.e. GFRP and mixed failure. The reference #A obviously shows a $P_{\#A, GFRP} = 100\%$ GFRP

Figure 12: Failure appearance of the specimens after the EST

failure mode. The chemically treated specimens of types #C1 and #C2 show both failure modes. Those of type #C1 have a predominant GFRP failure mode and those of type #C2 exhibit a predominant mixed failure mode.

For a discussion of the bearing strength of the pin joint with and without a local hybridization it is agreed upon, that specimens of type #GFRP2 (multidirectional GFRP) serve as the reference. The average bearing strength of each type of specimen is related to the averaged reference value (Fig. 10b). The average bearing strength of the specimens #Hybrid1 is equal to for the titanium dioxide primer or slightly better for the silane primer than that of the reference #GFRP2. By adding more steel layers the related average bearing strength becomes 2.4 for specimens #Hybrid4 with a silane primer and 2.2 for those with a titanium dioxide primer. In Fig. 13 the different average bearing strengths are plotted versus the specific steel content φ (Eq. 4). A linear relationship between the average bearing strength and the

Figure 13: Normalized bearing strength related to the specific steel content

specific steel content φ is obviously given to a specific steel content of 25 % for both primers. Both linear fits exhibits an intercept which is close to the average bearing strength of the specimens #GFRP1. The slope of the linear fit for the specimens #Hybrid1 to #Hybrid4 treated with titanium dioxide is slightly smaller compared to the slope of the fit for specimens #Hybrid1 to #Hybrid4 treated with silane.

The characteristic stresses within the specimens are discussed with the help of a simple mechanical model at example of specimen #Hybrid3. The balance of forces (s. Fig. 14) is analyzed at individual cross sections of the specimen. At cross section #1 the bearing load $F_{br} = F_{\#1}$ causes a pressure force

Figure 14: Stress situation in specimen #Hybrid3 at individual cross sections #1 to #3

at the cross section area in front of the pin. This force $F_{\#1}$ is split up into the forces $F_{\#1,steel}$ and $F_{\#1,GFRP}$ which describes the partition of forces transmitted into the steel and the GFRP, respectively, i.e.

$$F_{\#1} = F_{br} = F_{\#1,steel} + F_{\#1,GFRP} \quad (7)$$

At cross section #2 the force F_{br} is transmitted by two identical tensional loads into the structure beside the load “shadow” (s. Fig. 14). The corresponding forces $F_{\#2}$ are split up into the forces $F_{\#2,steel}$ and $F_{\#2,GFRP}$ which are transmitted into the corresponding layers, i.e.

$$F_{\#2} = \frac{1}{2} F_{br} = F_{\#2,GFRP} + F_{\#2,steel} \quad (8)$$

At cross section #3 it is assumed that the forces $F_{\#2,steel}$ are transmitted from the steel plates into the GFRP due to a homogeneous tensional load where the force $F_{\#3,steel}$ at each side of a steel plate is equal to one quarter of $2 \cdot F_{\#2,steel}$. The remaining force $F_{\#2,GFRP}$ is assumed to be directly transmitted into fibers in the proximity of cross section #2, so that the remaining fibers are not loaded by $F_{\#3,GFRP}$, i.e.

$$F_{\#3} = \frac{1}{4} \cdot 2 \cdot F_{\#2,steel} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot F_{\#2,steel} \quad (9)$$

For the sake of simplicity it is assumed that the forces $F_{\#1}$ and $F_{\#2}$ are entirely transmitted within the corresponding layers, i.e.

$$F_{\#1,steel} = 2 \cdot F_{\#2,steel} = 4 \cdot F_{\#3,steel} \quad \text{and} \quad F_{\#1,GFRP} = 2 \cdot F_{\#2,GFRP} \quad (10)$$

Furthermore, a homogeneous shear γ at cross section #2 is assumed, i.e. $\gamma_{\#2} = \gamma_{\#2,GFRP} = \gamma_{\#2,steel}$. The load partition is then given by

$$\frac{F_{\#2,GFRP}}{F_{\#2,steel}} = \frac{G_{GFRP} \cdot (1 - \varphi)}{G_{steel} \cdot \varphi} \quad (11)$$

With the shear moduli $G_{GFRP} \ll G_{steel}$. Considering a specific steel content $\varphi = 20\%$, it becomes clear, that $F_{\#2,steel}$ is significantly higher than $F_{\#2,GFRP}$. Considering shear modulus values $G_{GFRP} = 5.3 \text{ GPa}$ [8] and $G_{steel} = 79 \text{ GPa}$ the load partition of the bearing load F_{br} is split up by 21 % of F_{br} into the GFRP and 79 % of F_{br} into the steel. By using this simple model, a first estimation of the bearing normal stress $\sigma_{\#1}$, the shear stress $\tau_{\#2}$ in the cross section parallel to the shadow area behind the drill hole axis, and the shear stress $\tau_{\#3}$ in the laminate is given. The corresponding stresses within the layers then reads

$$\sigma_{\#1,GFRP} = \frac{0.21 \cdot F_{br}}{d \cdot t_{br} \cdot (1 - \varphi)} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_{\#1,steel} = \frac{0.79 \cdot F_{br}}{d \cdot t_{br} \cdot \varphi} \quad (12)$$

$$\tau_{\#2,\text{GFRP}} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{0.21 \cdot F_{\text{br}}}{3 \cdot d \cdot t_{\text{br}} \cdot (1 - \varphi)} \quad \text{and} \quad \tau_{\#2,\text{steel}} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{0.79 \cdot F_{\text{br}}}{3 \cdot d \cdot t_{\text{br}} \cdot \varphi} \quad (13)$$

$$\tau_{\#3} = \frac{1}{4} \frac{0.79 \cdot F_{\text{br}}}{w_{\text{br}} \cdot l_{\text{steel}} - 3 \cdot d^2 - 0.125 \cdot d^2 \cdot \pi} \quad (14)$$

where $t_{\text{br}} = 5$ mm is the thickness of the specimen, $d = 6$ mm the diameter of the drill hole, $w_{\text{br}} = 36$ mm the width of the specimen, and $l_{\text{steel}} = 40$ mm the length of the steel plate in the local hybridization of specimen #Hybrid3. By using this approach the following conclusions can be drawn. (i) The normal stress $\sigma_{\#1,\text{steel}}$ exceeds the yield strength $R_e = 1450$ MPa of the bainitic steel at a force $F_{\text{br}} > 11.6$ kN. (ii) The normal stress $\sigma_{\#1,\text{steel}}$ exceeds the tensile strength $R_m = 1800$ MPa of the bainitic steel at a force $F_{\text{br}} > 14.4$ kN. (iii) The normal stress $\sigma_{\#1,\text{GFRP}}$ exceeds the bearing strength $\bar{\sigma}_{\text{br},\#\text{GFRP1}} = 207$ MPa of the GFRP at a force $F_{\text{br}} > 23.4$ kN. (iv) The shear stress $\tau_{\#2,\text{GFRP}}$ exceeds the shear strength $\bar{\tau}_{s,\#\text{A}} = 55$ MPa of the GFRP at a force $F_{\text{br}} > 37.2$ kN. (v) At the maximum bearing force $F_{\text{br}} = 30$ kN the shear stress $\tau_{\#3} = 4.2$ MPa between steel and GFRP is still much smaller than the shear strength of the laminate (s. Fig. 5b). Since the finale failure occurs at a force far beyond the forces F_{br} reported in (i) to (iii) it is concluded that the local deformation of the steel at $F_{\text{br}} = 11.6$ kN and the bearing failure of GFRP at $F_{\text{br}} = 23.4$ kN is still compensated by the hybrid laminate. However, as soon as the shear stress $\tau_{\#2,\text{GFRP}}$ exceeds the shear strength $\tau_{s,\#\text{A}}$ of the GFRP in cross section #2 at forces far beyond $F_{\text{br}} = 30$ kN the hybrid laminate fails. This seems to indicate that a shear failure at cross section #2 determine the bearing strength of the hybrid laminate of specimen #Hybrid3. The simple mechanical model does not consider the deformations and damages that occur at forces beyond $F_{\text{br}} = 11.9$ kN. For a more precise description of the stresses another approach, e.g. by means of finite element analysis, is required.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The surface of the steel is chemically treated to improve the adhesion between the epoxy resin of the GFRP and the high strength steel. A DCB-Test (mode I) provides the energy release rate and the EST (mode II) the shear strength. The silan and titanium dioxide show a good bonding strength which is similar to that of the GFRP reference. A strengthening of the energy release rate, caused by a fiber bridging effect, is characterized by a strengthening exponent. A high strengthening exponent appears for the silane and titanium dioxide coated specimens which exhibit even higher energy release rates than the reference GFRP. A similar behavior is found for the crack resistances G_{Ic} which are highest for the silane and titanium dioxide coated specimens followed by GFRP. The tested specimens of the EST exhibit two different failure modes, i.e. a GFRP failure and a mixed failure mode. A high shear strength correlates with a dominant GFRP failure mode. The chemically treated specimens with silan and titanium dioxide exhibit, however, reduced shear strengths compared to the reference GFRP.

A pin joint with a local hybridization is characterized in a pull-out test. The local hybridization leads to a significant increase of the average bearing strength up to 2.4 times higher in comparison to the multidirectional GFRP reference. Furthermore, there is a linear correlation between the average bearing strength and the specific steel content of the pin joint. A simple mechanical model provides the stress analysis the localized hybrid at the pin joint.

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